

Research Article

Formulation and Characterization of Zolmitriptan Mucoadhesive Nanogel for Transmucosal Delivery in Migraine Therapy

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 02 Feb 2026

Keywords:

Zolmitriptan, Migraine, Mucoadhesive nanogel, Chitosan nanoparticles, Transmucosal drug delivery, Controlled release

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.18458359

ABSTRACT

Migraine is a prevalent and debilitating neurological disorder that requires rapid and effective therapeutic intervention. Zolmitriptan, a selective 5-HT_{1B/1D} receptor agonist, is widely used in the acute management of migraine; however, its conventional oral administration is limited by delayed onset of action, variable absorption, and reduced bioavailability due to first-pass metabolism and migraine-associated gastric stasis. The present study aims to formulate and evaluate a zolmitriptan-loaded mucoadhesive nanogel for effective transmucosal drug delivery to overcome these limitations. Zolmitriptan-loaded chitosan nanoparticles were prepared using the ionotropic gelation technique and subsequently incorporated into a mucoadhesive gel base to form a nanogel. The formulated nanoparticles and nanogels were characterized for physicochemical properties including particle size, zeta potential, drug loading, encapsulation efficiency, surface morphology, and compatibility using FTIR. The nanogel formulations were further evaluated for pH, viscosity, drug content, mucoadhesive strength, in vitro drug release, release kinetics, and stability under different storage conditions. The optimized formulation demonstrated nanoscale particle size, satisfactory encapsulation efficiency, strong mucoadhesive properties, and a controlled drug release profile following suitable kinetic models. Stability studies indicated no significant changes in formulation characteristics, confirming good physical stability. Overall, the developed zolmitriptan-loaded mucoadhesive nanogel shows promise as an alternative transmucosal delivery system, offering rapid onset of action, improved bioavailability, and enhanced patient compliance in migraine therapy.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a common, chronic, and debilitating neurological disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of moderate to severe headache, often

accompanied by nausea, vomiting, photophobia, and phonophobia. It affects nearly 12% of the global population and is more prevalent in women, particularly during their reproductive years.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Migraine significantly impacts quality of life, daily functioning, and work productivity, making it a major public health concern.

Migraine is a complex neurovascular disorder involving dysfunction of the trigeminovascular system, cortical spreading depression, neurogenic inflammation, and altered neurotransmitter signaling, particularly serotonin (5-HT). Activation of trigeminal nerve endings leads to the release of vasoactive neuropeptides such as calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP), resulting in vasodilation, inflammation, and pain transmission. Effective acute migraine management therefore requires rapid onset of action and reliable drug absorption.

Zolmitriptan, a selective 5-HT_{1B/1D} receptor agonist, is widely prescribed for the acute treatment of migraine attacks. It exerts its therapeutic action by constricting dilated cranial blood vessels, inhibiting neuropeptide release, and reducing central pain transmission. Despite its proven efficacy, conventional oral administration of zolmitriptan presents significant limitations, including delayed onset of action, variable absorption, and reduced bioavailability (~40–50%) due to extensive first-pass hepatic metabolism. Additionally, migraine-associated symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, and gastric stasis further compromise oral drug absorption and patient compliance.

To overcome these drawbacks, alternative drug delivery approaches capable of bypassing gastrointestinal barriers and hepatic first-pass metabolism are increasingly being explored. Transmucosal drug delivery systems—including nasal, buccal, and sublingual routes—offer several advantages such as rapid absorption, improved bioavailability, and enhanced patient compliance, particularly during acute migraine attacks. These routes allow direct drug absorption into systemic

circulation through highly vascularized mucosal tissues, enabling faster therapeutic effects.

In recent years, mucoadhesive nanogel-based delivery systems have gained considerable attention as advanced transmucosal drug carriers. Nanogels are hydrogel-based nanoparticles, typically ranging from 20–200 nm, capable of encapsulating both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. The application of mucoadhesive nanogels in migraine therapy offers distinct advantages, including rapid onset of action, reduced dosing frequency, improved bioavailability, and minimized systemic side effects. Intranasal or buccal nanogel formulations of triptans, such as zolmitriptan, may further enable direct nose-to-brain transport via the olfactory pathway, bypassing the blood–brain barrier and enhancing central nervous system targeting.

The present study focuses on the formulation and characterization of a zolmitriptan-loaded mucoadhesive nanogel for transmucosal delivery. The primary objectives are to enhance bioavailability, achieve rapid onset of therapeutic action, and improve patient compliance in migraine management. The developed formulation will be evaluated for physicochemical properties, mucoadhesive strength, *in vitro* drug release kinetics, and stability, thereby establishing its potential as an effective alternative to conventional oral migraine therapies.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim:

To formulate and characterize a zolmitriptan-loaded mucoadhesive nanogel for effective transmucosal delivery to enhance therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance in migraine therapy.

Objective:

1. To formulate zolmitriptan-loaded nanoparticles using suitable polymers and techniques.
2. To incorporate the prepared nanoparticles into a mucoadhesive gel base to form a nanogel.
3. To evaluate the prepared nanogel and study the stability of the optimized nanogel formulation.

3. DRUG PROFILE

Generic Name: Zolmitriptan

Chemical Class: Triptan (substituted tryptamine)

Molecular Formula: C₁₆H₂₁N₃O₂

Molecular Weight: 287.36 g/mol

Chemical Structure: Zolmitriptan is a derivative of N,N-dimethyltryptamine (DMT) in which the hydrogen atom at the 5-position of the indole ring is substituted with a [(4S)-2-oxo-1,3-oxazolidin-4-yl]methyl group (Figure 1).

Figure No: 1

Description:

Zolmitriptan is a selective serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine) receptor agonist belonging to the triptan class. It exhibits high affinity for 5-HT_{1B} and 5-HT_{1D} receptors and moderate affinity for 5-HT_{1F} receptors, with negligible activity at other serotonin receptor subtypes. It acts as a serotonergic agonist, vasoconstrictor, and anti-inflammatory agent and is widely used in the acute

treatment of migraine attacks. Zolmitriptan is a second-generation triptan developed to overcome the poor oral bioavailability and limited lipophilicity of first-generation agents such as sumatriptan. It was approved by the US FDA in 1997 and is marketed under brand names such as Zomig®.

Therapeutic Uses:

- Acute treatment of migraine with or without aura
- Acute treatment of cluster headaches
- Management of menstrual migraine (Zolmitriptan is not intended for migraine prophylaxis or for hemiplegic or basilar migraine.)

Pharmacological Mechanism of Action:

Zolmitriptan selectively activates 5-HT_{1B} and 5-HT_{1D} receptors, resulting in vasoconstriction of dilated intracranial blood vessels and inhibition of pro-inflammatory neuropeptide release (e.g., CGRP) from trigeminal nerve endings. This dual action reduces neurogenic inflammation and central pain transmission. Due to its lipophilicity, zolmitriptan is capable of crossing the blood-brain barrier and exerting central effects.

Pharmacokinetics:

Zolmitriptan exhibits rapid absorption, with an oral bioavailability of approximately 40% due to hepatic first-pass metabolism. It has a mean elimination half-life of about 3 hours. The drug is primarily metabolized by CYP1A2 to form an active metabolite, N-desmethylzolmitriptan, which contributes significantly to its therapeutic effect. Renal excretion is the main route of elimination. Food intake has no clinically significant effect on its absorption.

Physicochemical Properties:

- Solubility: Soluble in organic solvents (ethanol, DMSO, DMF); sparingly soluble in aqueous media
- Lipophilicity: Higher than first-generation triptans, facilitating CNS penetration

Available Dosage Forms:

- Oral tablets (2.5 mg and 5 mg)
- Orally disintegrating tablets
- Nasal spray

Clinical evidence suggests that the nasal spray provides faster and more effective relief compared to oral tablets.

Advanced Drug Delivery Approaches:

Recent research focuses on polymeric and nanocarrier-based delivery systems, including chitosan and PLGA-based nanoparticles, to enhance zolmitriptan bioavailability, achieve rapid onset of action, and improve brain targeting.

4. POLYMER PROFILE

4.1 Chitosan

Chemical Structure:

Chitosan (Figure 2) is a natural, cationic polysaccharide obtained by partial deacetylation of chitin, which is abundantly present in the exoskeletons of crustaceans such as shrimp and crabs. Structurally, it consists of β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-linked D-glucosamine and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine units arranged in a linear polymer chain.

Molecular Formula: $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{35}\text{N}_3\text{O}_{13}$

Molecular Weight: 501.5 g/mol

Description: Chitosan is a biodegradable, biocompatible, and non-toxic biopolymer with significant pharmaceutical importance. It is produced by alkaline deacetylation of chitin using agents such as sodium hydroxide. Owing to the presence of primary amino groups, chitosan exhibits a positive charge in acidic environments, enabling strong interactions with negatively charged biological membranes and macromolecules. These properties make chitosan particularly suitable for biomedical and drug delivery applications.

Physicochemical Properties: Chitosan is sparingly soluble in water and practically insoluble in ethanol and most organic solvents. It dissolves readily in dilute aqueous solutions of organic acids, where protonation of amino groups occurs, resulting in water-soluble chitosan salts. Its solubility is strongly influenced by pH and degree of deacetylation, with precipitation occurring at pH values above approximately 6.5. Chitosan exhibits a glass transition temperature of approximately 203°C and has a particle size typically below $30\ \mu\text{m}$. It is incompatible with strong oxidizing agents.

Pharmacokinetics: Following oral administration, chitosan is poorly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract and is primarily eliminated via feces. Limited degradation and metabolism may occur through gut microbiota. Due to its cationic nature, chitosan can interact with negatively charged biomolecules such as DNA, RNA, and proteins, influencing its distribution and functional behavior in biological systems.

Pharmaceutical Applications: Chitosan has been extensively studied as a polymer in drug delivery systems due to its mucoadhesive nature, ability to form nanoparticles, and capacity to enhance drug bioavailability. Chitosan-based nanoparticles provide controlled and sustained drug release, improved permeation across biological membranes, and prolonged residence time at the site of administration. In addition to drug delivery, chitosan is widely used in wound healing due to its antimicrobial and tissue-regenerative properties, in tissue engineering as a scaffold material, and in gene therapy for the delivery of nucleic acids such as plasmid DNA and siRNA.

5. PLAN OF WORK

Preformulation study:

- Determination of melting point
- Solubility study
- Calibration curve
- Compatibility using FTIR

Formulation of zolmitriptan nanoparticles Characterization of nanoparticles

- Entrapment efficacy
- Drug content
- In vitro dissolution studies
- Particle size, poly dispersity index and zetapotential
- Surface morphology

Formulation of mucoadhesive nanogel Evaluation of nanogel

- pH measurement
- Viscosity measurement
- Drug content
- Mucoadhesive strength
- In vitro dissolution study
- In vitro drug release kinetic study

6. MATERIALS AND METHODS

6.1 Materials

Zolmitriptan was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Chitosan was obtained from Nalinc Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mumbai. Sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP), glycerin, and methanol were purchased from Loba Chemie. HPMC and Tween-80 were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Acetic acid, ethanol, and methanol were sourced from Aldrich Co. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Table 1. Materials and Suppliers

Sr. No	Material	Supplier
1	Zolmitriptan	Sigma-Aldrich
2	Chitosan	Nalinc Pharmaceuticals Ltd., Mumbai
3	Sodium Tripolyphosphate	Loba Chemie
4	HPMC	Sigma-Aldrich
5	Glycerin	Loba Chemie
6	Acetic acid	Aldrich Co.
7	Ethanol	Aldrich Co.
8	Methanol	Aldrich Co.
9	Tween-80	Sigma-Aldrich

6.2 Instruments

Analytical and characterization instruments included a digital balance (Shimadzu BL-220H), dissolution apparatus (Labindia Disso 2000), FTIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu FTIR-8400S), particle size analyzer (AccuSizer 780), SEM (Hitachi S-450), UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu), pH meter (Systronics MK-VI), Brookfield viscometer, magnetic and mechanical stirrers (REMI), and stability chamber (REMI CHM-10S).

6.3 Preformulation Studies

6.3.1 Melting Point

The melting point of zolmitriptan was determined by the capillary method using 2–5 mg of sample to assess drug purity.

6.3.2 Solubility Study

Excess drug was added to various solvents (water, buffer saline, ethanol, methanol, ether, and ethanol:water). Samples were shaken at 25 ± 1 °C for 12 h, equilibrated for 24 h, centrifuged, filtered, and analyzed spectrophotometrically.

6.3.3 Calibration Curve

A stock solution (100 µg/mL) was prepared in methanol. Serial dilutions (2–12 µg/mL) were analyzed at 222 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometry, and a calibration curve was constructed.

6.3.4 FTIR Compatibility Study

Drug, polymers, and physical mixtures were analyzed using FTIR ($500\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) employing the KBr pellet method to detect any drug–excipient interactions.

6.4 Preparation of Zolmitriptan Nanoparticles

Zolmitriptan-loaded chitosan nanoparticles were prepared by the ionotropic gelation method. Chitosan was dissolved in 1% acetic acid, followed by incorporation of zolmitriptan and Tween-80 under stirring. TPP solution was added dropwise under mechanical stirring (4000 rpm, 30 min). pH was adjusted using 1N NaOH, and nanoparticles were isolated by centrifugation (12,000 rpm)

Table 2. Composition of Nanoparticle Formulations

Formulation	Drug %	Chitosan %	TPP %	Tween-80 %	NaOH %
F1–F10	0.5	0.05–0.55	0.75	0.25	1.5

6.5 Characterization of Nanoparticles

Drug Content & Encapsulation Efficiency:

Nanoparticles were centrifuged (10,000 rpm, 30 min). Free drug in supernatant was quantified at 222 nm. EE% and LC% were calculated using standard equations.

In vitro Drug Release: USP Type II apparatus was used with hydroalcoholic medium (70:30 water:ethanol) at 37 ± 0.5 °C. Samples were withdrawn at intervals up to 90 min and analyzed spectrophotometrically.

Release Kinetics: Release data were fitted to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas models to determine release mechanism.

Particle Size & Zeta Potential: Measured by dynamic light scattering after suitable dilution.

Zeta potential was used to assess colloidal stability.

Surface Morphology: SEM was used to study particle shape, size, and surface characteristics.

6.6 Stability Study of Nanoparticles

Optimized nanoparticles were stored at 4 °C and 25 °C for three months. Particle size, PDI, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency were periodically evaluated.

6.7 Formulation of Zolmitriptan Nanogel

Nanoparticles were incorporated into an HPMC-based mucoadhesive gel. HPMC concentration was varied (0.4–0.55% w/w), glycerin (5% w/w) served as humectant, and sodium benzoate (0.01% w/w) as preservative. pH was adjusted to 6.4–6.8.

Table 3. Nanogel Composition

Ingredient	Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4
HPMC (%)	0.4	0.45	0.5	0.55
Glycerin (%)	5	5	5	5
Sodium benzoate (%)	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Water	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.

6.8 Evaluation of Nanogel

pH, viscosity, drug content, mucoadhesive strength, in vitro drug release, and release kinetics were evaluated using standard methods. Mucoadhesive strength was determined using a modified balance method with porcine buccal mucosa.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Preformulation Studies

7.1.1 Melting Point

The melting point of zolmitriptan was determined by the capillary tube method and found to be **143°C**. Melting point determination is a critical preformulation parameter that provides insight into the purity, crystalline nature, and thermal stability of a drug substance. The observed value closely matches reported literature values, indicating that the zolmitriptan sample used in the study was of high purity and suitable for formulation development.

7.1.2 Solubility Studies

Solubility studies revealed that zolmitriptan is freely soluble in methanol and ethanol, moderately soluble in water and buffered saline, and poorly

soluble in non-polar solvents such as ether (Table 5). The moderate aqueous solubility supports its suitability for transmucosal formulations. A hydroalcoholic mixture (30:70 ethanol:water) was selected for dissolution and in vitro release studies to enhance solubility and maintain sink conditions, ensuring reliable evaluation of drug release behavior.

Table 4: solubility studies

Solvent	Nature of solubility
Ethanol	Soluble
Ether	Poorly soluble
Water	Moderately soluble
Methanol	Soluble
Buffered saline	Moderately soluble
Ethanol: distilled water (30:70)	Soluble

7.1.3 Calibration Curve

A UV-visible spectrophotometric calibration curve for zolmitriptan was developed at 222 nm over a concentration range of 0–50 µg/mL. The calibration plot showed excellent linearity, following the equation $y = 0.018x + 0.010$, with a correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9998$ (Table 6). This confirms the suitability of the method for accurate quantitative estimation of zolmitriptan in subsequent studies

Table 5: calibration curve

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance
0	0
10	0.21
20	0.46
30	0.65
40	0.82
50	0.99

7.1.4 FTIR Compatibility Study

FTIR spectroscopy was performed to evaluate the compatibility between zolmitriptan and formulation excipients, including chitosan, sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP), and Tween 80. Characteristic peaks corresponding to N–H, O–H, C=N, C–N, and aromatic C–H stretching

vibrations were preserved in the physical mixture with only minor shifts in wavenumbers. These slight variations indicate physical interactions such as hydrogen bonding or ionic association, rather than chemical incompatibility. Overall, the FTIR results confirmed that zolmitriptan is compatible with the selected excipients and suitable for nanoparticle formulation.

Figure No: 3 - FTIR of zolmitriptan

Figure No: 4 – FTIR of chitosan

Figure No: 5 – FTIR of Tripolyphosphate (TPP)

Figure No: 6 – FTIR of tween 80

Table no: 6

Functional group	Zolmitriptan	Chitosan	Tripolyphosphate	Tween 80	Physical mixture
N-H stretching	3325.40	3354.71	3383.26	3420.00	3329.00
C-H stretching	2964.80	2919.36	2835.45	2960.83	2949.26
C=N stretching	1675.25	1652.09	-	1739.00	1652.00
N-H bending	-	1595.00	-	-	1590.00
C-H bending	754.20	1451.48	-	1456.00	1455.34
C-N stretching	1248.65	-	-	-	1245.00
Ether stretching	-	1098	-	1150.00	1100.00
P=O stretching	-	-	1238.00	-	1240.00
P-O-P stretching	-	-	883.00	-	883.00

7.2 Evaluation of Zolmitriptan Nanoparticles

7.2.1 Encapsulation Efficiency

The encapsulation efficiency of zolmitriptan nanoparticles ranged from 72.4% to 89.7% across formulations F1–F10 (Table 7). Formulation F5 exhibited the highest encapsulation efficiency ($89.7 \pm 0.9\%$), indicating optimal polymer–drug interaction and efficient entrapment. The results demonstrate that formulation variables significantly influence drug encapsulation.

Table 7: Encapsulation efficiency

Formulation	Encapsulation efficiency (%)
F1	72.4±1.3
F2	75.6±1.1
F3	78.9±1.2
F4	82.1±1.0
F5	89.7±0.9
F6	87.3±1.1
F7	85.5±1.4
F8	82.9±1.2
F9	79.3±1.5
F10	76.5±1.3

7.2.2 Drug Loading Capacity

Drug loading capacity varied between 68.5% and 84.6% (Table 8). Formulation F5 showed the highest drug loading ($84.6 \pm 1.0\%$), confirming its superiority among the tested formulations. Based on encapsulation efficiency and drug loading results, F5 was selected for further characterization and development.

Table 8: Drug loading capacity

Formulation code	Drug loading capacity (%)
F1	68.5 ± 1.4
F2	71.2 ± 1.1
F3	74.8 ± 1.3
F4	78.1 ± 1.2
F5	84.6 ± 1.0
F6	82.3 ± 1.4
F7	80.2 ± 1.6
F8	77.9 ± 1.3
F9	74.5 ± 1.7
F10	71.1 ± 1.5

7.2.3 In Vitro Drug Release

The in vitro release profile of formulation F5 demonstrated a controlled and sustained release of zolmitriptan. An initial release of 23.10% was observed, followed by gradual drug release reaching $\sim 99.85\%$ at the end of the study (Table 9). This sustained release behavior suggests that the nanoparticle system can potentially reduce dosing frequency and enhance therapeutic efficacy in migraine management.

Table 9: invitro drug release

Time (h)	Absorbance	Conc (μ /ml)	Conc (mg/ml)	Conc*df	Error	Bath conc	Drug release	% DR
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0.234	32.05	0.03	0.33	0.33	11.25	11.25	23.10
2	0.451	50.94	0.06	0.54	0.84	17.45	18.97	37.42
4	0.578	67.23	0.08	0.64	1.54	23.87	26.71	50.89
5	0.642	84.23	0.9	0.85	2.13	28.64	31.56	59.71
6	0.794	98.65	0.10	0.99	2.35	31.65	35.78	63.78
8	0.863	110.84	0.10	1.01	3.32	35.87	37.47	74.31
10	0.892	119.21	0.11	1.10	4.42	38.91	42.89	85.64
11	0.951	122.68	0.11	1.19	5.60	41.89	46.71	95.01
12	0.993	124.98	0.12	1.23	6.83	43.87	49.32	99.85

Table 10: invitro kinetic study

% CR	Time (T)	Root T	Log (%) release	Log (T)	Log (%) remain	Release (Cum Rls/ T)	1/Cum % Rls	Peppas log Q/100	% DR	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3 - Qt1/3
0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23.10	2	0.0	0.00	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	100	4.64	4.64	0.00
37.42	4	0.5	1.57	0.60	1.89	5.78	2.00	-0.43	76.9	4.64	4.25	0.39
50.89	5	1.0	1.71	0.70	1.80	7.48	1.00	-0.43	62.58	4.64	3.97	0.67
59.71	6	2.0	1.78	0.78	1.69	8.48	0.50	-0.29	49.11	4.64	3.66	0.98
63.78	8	4.0	1.80	0.90	1.61	7.46	0.25	-0.22	40.29	4.64	3.43	1.21
74.31	10	6.0	1.87	1.00	1.56	6.38	0.17	-0.20	36.22	4.64	3.31	1.33
85.64	12	8.0	1.93	1.08	1.41	6.19	0.13	-0.13	25.69	4.64	2.95	1.69
95.01	18	10.0	1.98	1.26	1.16	4.76	0.10	-0.07	14.36	4.64	2.43	2.21
99.85	24	12.0	2.00	1.38	0.70	3.96	0.08	-0.02	4.99	4.64	1.71	2.93

7.2.4 Release Kinetic Study

Release kinetics of formulation F5 were analyzed using zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models. The release data best

fitted the Higuchi model, indicating a diffusion-controlled release mechanism. This suggests that zolmitriptan diffuses gradually through the polymeric nanoparticle matrix, ensuring prolonged drug release.

Table 11: particle size analysis

Formulation	Particle size(nm)	Polydispersity Index (PDI)
F5	160.3	0.254

Formulation F5 exhibited an average particle size of 160.3 nm with a PDI of 0.254, indicating a relatively uniform nanoparticle population (Table 11). Zeta potential analysis revealed a surface charge of -32.5 mV, confirming good colloidal stability and reduced particle aggregation.

7.2.5 Particle Size and Zeta Potential

Zeta potential distribution

Results

Mean zeta potential
 \pm Standard deviation
 Distribution peak
 Electrophoretic mobility

-32.5 mV
 1.7 mV
 -31.2 mV
 -2.3772 $\mu\text{m}^2\text{cm/Vs}$

Mean intensity
 Filter optical density
 Conductivity
 Transmittance

567.6 counts/s
 3.7384
 0.036 mS/cm
 76.1 %

7.2.6 Surface Morphology

SEM analysis showed that the nanoparticles were spherical in shape with smooth surfaces,

Figure No: 8 – Surface Morphology

7.2.7 Stability Study of Nanoparticles

Stability studies conducted at 4°C and 25°C demonstrated negligible changes in encapsulation efficiency, drug loading, particle size, PDI, and zeta potential (Table 12). The results confirm the physical stability of formulation F5 under the tested storage conditions.

Table 12: Stability studies

For F5	4°C	25°C
%EE	89.65±0.9	90.01±0.2
Drug loading capacity	84.7±1.0	85.2±0.2
Particle size	160.5±3.5	161.7±3.0
Polydispersity index	0.25	0.26
Zetapotential	32.5mv	33.5mv

7.3 Formulation and Evaluation of Zolmitriptan Nanogel

Four nanoparticle-loaded mucoadhesive gel formulations (Z1–Z4) were prepared by varying the concentration of HPMC while keeping other components constant.

7.3.1 pH, Viscosity, and Drug Content

All gel formulations exhibited a pH range of 6.3–6.8, suitable for transmucosal application. Viscosity increased with increasing HPMC concentration, with Z3 (0.5% HPMC) showing

supporting uniform drug encapsulation and predictable release behavior.

optimal viscosity for mucosal retention. Drug content ranged from 95% to 99.54%, indicating uniform drug distribution

Table 13: pH

Formulation	pH
Z1	6.4
Z2	6.3
Z3	6.5
Z4	6.4

Table 14: viscosity

Formulation	Viscosity (cps)
Z1	12150
Z2	12740
Z3	15600
Z4	23559

7.3.2 Mucoadhesive Strength

Mucoadhesive strength increased with polymer concentration. Formulation Z3 showed the highest mucoadhesive force (2.45 N), suggesting improved retention at the site of application and enhanced drug absorption.

Table 15:mucoadhesive strength

Formulation	Mucoadhesive strength (g)	Force of adhesion (N)
Z1	18	1.76
Z2	21	2.05
Z3	25	2.45
Z4	23	2.26

7.3.3 In Vitro Drug Release and Kinetics

Formulation Z3 exhibited sustained drug release, reaching ~99.1% within 12 hours (Table 17).

Kinetic modeling showed the best fit to the Higuchi model, confirming diffusion-controlled release from the gel matrix

Table 16 : invitro drug release

Time	Absorbance	Conc (µ/ml)	Conc (mg/ml)	Conc*df	Error	Bath conc	Drug release	%DR
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0.214	33.64	0.03	0.54	0.54	23.47	24.61	45.12
4	0.350	56.77	0.08	0.59	0.97	24.56	23.75	46.31
5	0.487	88.76	0.9	0.67	1.43	31.78	33.61	66.32
6	0.511	98.66	0.10	0.74	2.17	35.97	37.16	75.61
8	0.623	115.20	0.11	1.01	3.11	36.68	38.75	76.51
10	0.894	130.24	0.13	1.13	5.44	38.14	44.33	89.99
12	0.995	134.49	0.16	1.25	6.12	45.77	49.54	99.1

Cumulative (%) Release Q	Time (T)	Root (T)	Log(%) Release	Log(T)	Log(%) Remain	Release Rate (Cumulative % Release / T)	1/Cum % Release	Peppas Log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
45.12	0.5	0.707	1.654	-0.301	1.739	90.240	0.0222	-0.346	54.88	4.642	3.800	0.841
46.31	1	1.000	1.666	0.000	1.730	46.310	0.0216	-0.334	53.69	4.642	3.773	0.869
66.32	2	1.414	1.822	0.301	1.527	33.160	0.0151	-0.178	33.68	4.642	3.229	1.412
75.61	4	2.000	1.879	0.602	1.387	18.903	0.0132	-0.121	24.39	4.642	2.900	1.742
76.51	8	2.828	1.884	0.903	1.371	9.564	0.0131	-0.116	23.49	4.642	2.864	1.778
89.99	10	3.162	1.954	1.000	1.000	8.999	0.0111	-0.046	10.01	4.642	2.155	2.486
99.1	12	3.464	1.996	1.079	-0.046	8.258	0.0101	-0.004	0.9	4.642	0.965	3.676

7.4 Stability Study of Nanogel

Formulation Z3 remained physically stable at 4°C/60% RH and 25°C/75% RH over 30 days,

with no evidence of phase separation, crystallization, or consistency changes (Table 18). These findings confirm the stability and suitability of Z3 for transmucosal delivery.

Table 17: Stability studies

Formulation (Z3)	Colour	Phase separation	Crystallization	Consistency changes
At 4°C	None	None	None	None
25°C	None	None	None	None

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HOW TO CITE: R Suresh Kumar, S Divyadharshini, Formulation and Characterization of Zolmitriptan Mucoadhesive Nanogel for Transmucosal Delivery in Migraine Therapy, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 2, 213-227. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18458359>

